

Mathematics Curriculum Reform in Irish Primary Schools: Encouraging Faithful Implementation

Sarah Porcenaluk and Cornelia Connolly

University of Galway

Ireland's Primary Mathematics Curriculum is undergoing a critical reformation emphasising developing students as mathematicians (National Council for Curriculum and Assessment, 2020). Students will be called upon to problem-solve, analyse, and synthesise information. To understand how students are progressing through learning these valuable 21st-century skills, teachers must use formative assessment to inform and adjust instruction (Burkhardt & Schoenfeld, 2019). Teachers will require additional support through continued professional development (CPD) to transition to this new curriculum and increased focus on formative assessment (Spillane & Thompson, 1997). This paper provides an overview of Ireland's developing primary mathematics curriculum, discusses how assessment must progress alongside it, and links a curriculum's success to effective CPD. Finally, this paper reports on a current research study aiming to develop a toolkit that supports teachers in asking higher-level thinking questions in primary mathematics lessons. Teachers who effectively assess students' higher-level thinking will be better positioned to adjust instruction to help students develop as mathematicians.

Keywords: primary mathematics, teacher questioning, professional development

Introduction

Mathematics curriculums worldwide are being examined and revised to assist students in developing skills which prepare them for 21st-century challenges (Australian Curriculum Assessment and Reporting Authority, 2022; Ministry of Education, 2020; National Council of Curriculum and Assessment [NCCA], 2020). Although student achievement in mathematics has increased recently, students simultaneously fall short in demonstrating higher-level thinking skills such as problem-solving, analysing, and synthesising (Mullis et al., 2020). Therefore, curriculum developers and educational institutions have recognised a considerable need in mathematics classrooms and have begun to act through curriculum reform.

This paper aims to give insight into mathematics curriculum reform currently happening in Ireland. We highlight that primary teachers in Ireland may need to make significant changes to their approaches to teaching mathematics and will need continued professional development (CPD) opportunities to do so. To support this viewpoint, we give an example of the role of formative assessment in Ireland's Draft Primary Mathematics Curriculum (DPMC). In addition, we also give a brief overview of an in-progress research study on designing a teacher toolkit for implementing higher-level questioning into mathematics lessons with the following research questions:

- (a) Can we collaboratively develop a toolkit for primary teachers on effectively incorporating questioning in mathematics?
- (b) Will the toolkit positively impact teachers' instruction, and to what degree? Will it act as a form of continued professional development, expanding teachers' knowledge of teaching mathematics?

- (c) How can this research contribute to education theories on mathematics education and continued professional development?

As this research is in its formative stages, this paper does not intend to provide in-depth answers to the research questions but rather spark a discussion around faithful curriculum implementation during periods of change and give meaning and purpose to an ongoing study, discussed in the second half of the paper.

Primary Mathematics Curriculum Reform in Ireland

Similar to countries worldwide, Ireland is undergoing periods of curriculum reform. The primary mathematics curriculum is being revised to reflect the needs of students and teachers to increase academic achievement (NCCA, 2020). The NCCA has released numerous reports in the last eight years which review the current state of primary mathematics education and recommend specific steps to increase students' academic progress (Burke, 2014; Dooley, 2019; NCCA, 2016). The DPMC was subsequently released in 2022.

The DPMC focuses on shaping students into mathematicians with mathematical proficiency. Mathematical proficiency is developed through learning to connect information, communicate effectively, construct and justify arguments, and analyse solutions (Ball, 2003). Therefore, the draft curriculum concentrates on procedural fluency, strategic competence, adaptive reasoning, productive disposition, and conceptual understanding (NCCA, 2022). While incorporating these skills into mathematics education is not new, the draft curriculum emphasises students developing these skills by refining how mathematics is taught.

Role of Formative Assessment

The DPMC intertwines formative assessment as a critical pedagogical practice to ensure students' academic success (NCCA, 2022). While summative assessments, such as end-of-unit exams or standardised tests, remain a primary method for measuring academic achievement, formative assessments are becoming integral to curriculums worldwide (Ministry of Education, 2020; New York State Education Department, 2017). Formative assessment can employ various approaches, but all methods aim for teachers to understand students' progression daily and make appropriate adjustments to instruction frequently (William, 2011).

Incorporating effective questioning methods into mathematics lessons is one method of using formative assessment (Palm et al., 2017). Integrating dialogue into mathematics lessons, including asking higher-level thinking questions, can help teachers identify specific student learning needs (Zack & Graves, 2002). As a result, Irish teachers must include higher-level questioning in their lessons to fully implement the new primary mathematics curriculum. However, effectively using questions in mathematics lessons is complex (Dillon, 2004) and often a challenging pedagogical skill to master (Fennema et al., 1996). Teachers should plan lessons with questions to ask students that span all cognitive levels (Shahrill, 2013). Unfortunately, teachers often stick to asking questions of lower cognitive levels and fail to fully understand how to interpret student responses and react accordingly (Moyer &

Milewicz, 2002). Therefore, to fully implement the new curriculum as written, Irish teachers must further develop questioning skills to incorporate formative assessment fully.

Adjustments to Teacher Practice in Coordination with Curriculum Implementation

Effective implementation of a new curriculum requires teachers to understand the curriculum's components fully and have the necessary pedagogical skills (Spillane & Thompson, 1997). Each teacher possesses various skills, pedagogical knowledge, and beliefs about teaching (König et al., 2015). Therefore, the changes to instruction each teacher may need to make during curriculum reform may differ between individuals.

The NCCA consulted with primary teachers to understand their perceptions of the draft curriculum and identify the skills teachers may need support with once a new curriculum is enacted (Bryne et al., 2023). Questionnaire results indicated that around half of teachers were unsure or did not believe the draft curriculum would help students develop mathematical proficiency (Bryne et al., 2023). Teachers who disagree with a curriculum's aims and goals will lack buy-in, and how it is implemented may be negatively affected. Without teachers understanding the underpinning research which supports a curriculum, there is a risk of it being implemented incorrectly or incompletely (Broadhead, 2001). In addition, the questionnaire aimed to understand how formative assessment fits with teachers' current approaches to teaching mathematics. Only 35% of teachers identified that formative assessment corresponds with their current practices, while the majority said it only matched to some degree (Bryne et al., 2023). While these questionnaire results may not indicate the needs of every primary teacher, it signals that many teachers may need to adjust their approach to teaching mathematics.

Role of Continued Professional Development Alongside Curriculum Reform

Continued professional development is essential to help teachers teach any curriculum (Radford, 1998). The structure of CPD which occurs alongside curriculum reform, should be considered early on. Despite various approaches to CPD, commonalities exist among methods, such as ensuring the content connects to teachers' practice, considers time and capacity barriers, and meets the individual needs of teachers (Hargreaves, 2014; Kennedy, 2014; Loucks-Horsley et al., 2009). To construct CPD that meets the diverse needs of teachers, a necessary first step is to evaluate the current approach to professional learning. This process should include understanding teachers' experiences with CPD and their recommendations for future CPD opportunities (King, 2014).

Current Approach to Continued Professional Development in Ireland

In Ireland, CPD is provided mainly through the Professional Development Service for Teachers (PDST), funded by the Teacher Education Section of the Department of Education. Through the PDST, numerous supports are available, including online and in-person workshops for teachers, school support, and access to various publications written by the PDST. In addition, the Teaching Council in Ireland released *Cosán: Framework for Teachers' Learning* in March 2016, guiding teachers' professional learning and growth during all stages

of an individual's teaching career (The Teaching Council, 2017). This framework identifies core principles for professional learning, such as teachers being autonomous learners, flexibility in education, and access to quality CPD (The Teaching Council, 2017).

To aid in writing this framework, the Teaching Council consulted teachers in 2014 through online surveys and in-person feedback. This consultation identified that teachers desire high-quality CPD connected to their classrooms while offering CPD choices (The Teaching Council, 2016), mirroring teachers' sentiments worldwide (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2019). Notably, the data analysis from the Teaching Council also revealed that the time required for CPD, access to workshops, cost, and required teacher capacity were of great concern to teachers (The Teaching Council, 2016). A striking theme emerging from the data is that teachers felt their concerns and suggestions would be discounted (The Teaching Council, 2016). Teachers being treated as professionals and with respect is indicative of a successful education system (Sachs, 2016). Structuring CPD opportunities and guidelines should consider teachers' perspectives, concerns, and suggestions to meet teachers' needs.

Methodology

The remaining discussion centres around an educational design-based research study conducted in Galway, Ireland. The researcher collaborated with six primary teachers to design a toolkit to guide teachers through using questioning effectively in lessons. All DEIS primary schools within Galway City were invited to participate, with a goal to recruit 6-10 teachers. The University of Galway provided ethical approval, and informed consent was received by all participants at the start.

Three design cycles were carried out to develop the toolkit. Teachers used the toolkit in their classrooms for six weeks during each cycle, followed by focus groups to analyse the toolkit and identify necessary adjustments. Observations of teacher instruction, researcher memos from teacher conversations, and additional anonymous questionnaires were also used. The questionnaires asked teachers to provide insight into their experiences using the toolkit and any desired changes. Data from focus groups were analysed with guidance from Galletta and Cross' interactive data analysis process, which included: becoming familiar with the qualitative data from the interview transcripts, generating and assigning codes to the text, looking for thematic patterns, and synthesising the codes into categories (2013). Analysis from the second design cycle's focus group interviews, completed in 2023, guides the discussion below.

Findings

Through focus group analysis, themes emerged from teachers' insights on resources that would help them teach mathematics. During the interview, the conversation diverted from the toolkit's development and toward the draft mathematics curriculum. It should be noted that these teachers indicated only basic knowledge of the draft curriculum. Therefore, in analysing teachers' responses on what might assist them in enacting the draft curriculum, it is essential to recognise teachers' limited knowledge of it.

Teachers made it clear that the mathematics textbook is integral to teaching mathematics. Teachers view the textbook as a method to keep them on track with teaching all the required content. One teacher commented:

Tadgh: If there isn't structure of the book, you do end up kinda going down a rabbit hole on a topic and going, 'Oh! This is great, and we're having a great time doing this; jeez, that two weeks gone on something that should have taken half an hour.

As a follow-up to this teacher's comment, the moderator asked the teachers if they believed resources, such as the toolkit being developed, should be designed to be used alongside textbooks. Teachers agreed that the textbook should come first and then additional resources used to support instruction. Another teacher indicated they use the textbooks to extend learning, stating:

Brian: And if you have three or four different maths textbooks and the topic is finished and you go here...we're going to try this one. And then, the guy in the middle is struggling; at least you have something to work with.

Teachers indicated that differentiating was easier with textbooks and that if the new curriculum focuses more on single in-depth tasks, this would be a significant challenge in the classroom. In addition, teachers indicated in this case that they would still utilise textbooks. The same teacher commented:

Brian: So, yes, we have the tasks, and we have that, but we're doing it in conjunction with the book. Because, when you have, like, you know, in my class, I have to differentiate all the time.

As part of this research project, the researcher travels to the primary school one day per week to work alongside the teachers. In the four mainstream classrooms, textbooks were used 100% of the time when the researcher supported the teachers with their lessons, which mirrors the teachers' comments in the interview.

Discussion and Conclusion

As the NCCA develops a new primary mathematics curriculum and decides how to support teachers through its implementation, it is critical to investigate teachers' current experiences and perspectives. The success of CPD can be increased if teachers see the learning as directly connected to their classrooms and consider their learning preferences (Loucks-Horsley et al., 2009). During this research, teachers indicated strong dependence on a mathematics textbook. The new draft curriculum focuses on students developing mathematical proficiency, including problem-solving, analysing, and synthesising skills. Yet, reports indicate that textbooks often fall short in aiding students in developing these higher-level thinking skills (Dooley, 2019). Similarly to the cohort of teachers in this research project, data across Ireland indicated that 91.5% of sixth-class teachers utilised a textbook daily (Dooley, 2019). If the new primary mathematics curriculum is to depend less on

textbook use, the NCCA needs to examine how teachers can be supported in making this transition.

The NCCA indicates an upcoming shift in teaching mathematics to develop students as mathematicians with critical thinking skills (NCCA, 2022). This pathway may require rethinking the use of textbooks, which primary teachers commonly use in daily instruction. As a result of the focus group interviews, it was clear that teachers needed resources that would provide some structure to lessons while also allowing for differentiating instruction. While the toolkit developed in this research project aims to aid teachers in asking higher-level thinking questions, it is not a textbook or lesson plans. CPD will be necessary to educate teachers on developing lesson plans that utilise formative assessment methods. It is crucial for those developing and facilitating CPD alongside the new curriculum's adoption to use teacher' voice to guide professional learning (Gozali et al., 2017). If CPD facilitators cannot obtain teacher buy-in, the curriculum may fail to be fully implemented, ultimately resulting in students' academic success suffering.

References

- Australian Curriculum Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2022). *Australian Curriculum: Foundation-Year 10 (Version 9.0)*. <https://v9.australiancurriculum.edu.au/>
- Ball, D. L. (2003). Teaching and Learning Mathematical Practices. In *Mathematical Proficiency for All Students: Toward a Strategic Research and Development Program in Mathematics Education* (pp. 29-42). <http://www.jstor.org.nuigalway.idm.oclc.org/stable/10.7249/mr1643oeri.10>
- Broadhead, P. (2001). Curriculum change in Norway: Thematic approaches, active learning and pupil cooperation - from curriculum design to classroom implementation. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 45(1), 19-36. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313830020023375>
- Bryne, M., O'Callaghan, A., Hannafin, M., & Monnelly, A. (2023). Report on the consultation on the Draft Primary Mathematics Curriculum. <https://ncca.ie/en/resources/consultation-report-pmc/>
- Burke, D. (2014). *Audit of mathematics curriculum policy across 12 jurisdictions*. <https://ncca.ie/media/2031/audit-mathematics-curriculum-policy.pdf>
- Dillon, J. T. (2004). *Questioning and teaching: A manual of practice*. Wipf and Stock Publishers.
- Dooley, T. (2019). *Learning and teaching primary mathematics: An addendum to NCCA research reports*. https://ncca.ie/media/4087/primary_maths_research_addendum_2019.pdf
- Fennema, E., Carpenter, T. P., Franke, M. L., Levi, L., Jacobs, V. R., & Empson, S. B. (1996). A longitudinal study of learning to use children's thinking in mathematics instruction. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 27(4), 403. <https://doi.org/10.2307/749875>
- Galletta, A., & Cross, W. E. (2013). *Mastering the Semi-Structured Interview and Beyond : From Research Design to Analysis and Publication*. New York University Press. <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/nuig/detail.action?docID=1187368>

- Gozali, C., Claassen-Thrush, E., Soto-Peña, M., Whang, C., & Luschei, T. (2017). Teacher Voice in Global Conversations around Education Access, Equity, and Quality. FIRE: forum for international research in education,
- Hargreaves, A. (2014). *Handbook of professional development in education: Successful models and practices, PreK-12*. Guilford Publications.
- Kennedy, A. (2014). Understanding continuing professional development: the need for theory to impact on policy and practice. *Professional Development in Education*, 40(5), 688-697. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2014.955122>
- King, F. (2014). Evaluating the impact of teacher professional development: an evidence-based framework. *Professional Development in Education*, 40(1), 89-111. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2013.823099>
- König, J., Blömeke, S., & Kaiser, G. (2015). Early career mathematics teachers' general pedagogical knowledge and skills: Do teacher education, teaching experience, and working conditions make a difference? *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 13(2), 331-350. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-015-9618-5>
- Loucks-Horsley, S., Stiles, K. E., Mundry, S. E., Love, N. B., & Hewson, P. W. (2009). *Designing Professional Development for Teachers of Science and Mathematics*. Corwin Press. <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/nuig/detail.action?docID=996256>
- Ministry of Education. (2020). The Ontario Curriculum Grades 1-8: Mathematics. <https://www.dcp.edu.gov.on.ca/en/curriculum/elementary-mathematics>
- Moyer, P. S., & Milewicz, E. (2002). Learning to question: Categories of questioning used by preservice teachers during diagnostic mathematics interviews. *Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education*, 5(4), 293-315. <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1021251912775>
- Mullis, I.V.S., Martin, M.O., Foy, P., Kelly, D.L., & Fishbein, B. (2020). *TIMSS 2019 International Results in Mathematics and Science*. <https://timss2019.org/reports>
- National Council of Curriculum and Assessment. (2016). *Background Paper and Brief for the Development of a new Primary Mathematics Curriculum*. https://ncca.ie/media/1341/maths_background_paper_131016_tc.pdf
- National Council of Curriculum and Assessment. (2020). *Draft Primary Curriculum Framework For Consultation*. <https://ncca.ie/en/resources/draft-primary-mathematics-curriculum-dr%C3%A9acht-churaclam-matamaitice-na-bunscoile/>
- National Council of Curriculum and Assessment. (2022). *Primary Mathematics Curriculum Draft specification for consultation*. <https://ncca.ie/en/resources/draft-primary-mathematics-curriculum-dr%C3%A9acht-churaclam-matamaitice-na-bunscoile/>
- New York State Education Department. (2017). *English Language Arts Learning Standards*. Albany, NY. <http://www.nysed.gov/curriculum-instruction/new-york-state-next-generation-english-language-arts-learning-standards>
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2019). *TALIS 2018 Results (Volume I)*. <https://doi.org/doi:https://doi.org/10.1787/1d0bc92a-en>
- Palm, T., Andersson, C., Boström, E., & Vingsle, C. (2017). A review of the impact of formative assessment on student achievement in mathematics. *Nordic Studies in Mathematics Education*, 22(3), 25-50.

- Radford, D. L. (1998). Transferring theory into practice: A model for professional development for science education reform. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 35(1), 73-88. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1098-2736\(199801\)35:1<73::AID-TEA5>3.0.CO;2-K](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1098-2736(199801)35:1<73::AID-TEA5>3.0.CO;2-K)
- Sachs, J. (2016). Teacher professionalism: why are we still talking about it? *Teachers and Teaching*, 22(4), 413-425. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2015.1082732>
- Shahrill, M. (2013). Review of effective teacher questioning in mathematics classrooms. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(17), 224-231.
- Spillane, J. P., & Thompson, C. L. (1997). Reconstructing conceptions of local capacity: The local education agency's capacity for ambitious instructional reform. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 19(2), 185-203. <https://doi.org/10.3102/01623737019002185>
- The Teaching Council. (2016). Development of the Cosán Framework: Drafting and Consultation Background Paper. <https://www.teachingcouncil.ie/en/publications/teacher-education/development-of-the-cosan-framework.pdf>
- The Teaching Council. (2017). *Cosán Framework for Teachers' Learning* <https://www.teachingcouncil.ie/en/Publications/Teacher-Education/Cosan-Framework-for-Teachers-Learning.pdf>
- Wiliam, D. (2011). *Embedded formative assessment*. Solution Tree Press.
- Zack, V., & Graves, B. (2002). Making mathematical meaning through dialogue: "Once you think of it, the Z minus three seems pretty weird". *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 46, 229-271.